

Design and Construction of a Solar Powered Tri-Cycle

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Abstract

The rapid depletion of fossil fuel reserves and the pressing need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions have necessitated the exploration of sustainable and eco-friendly transportation alternatives. This paper presents the design, construction, and evaluation of a solar-powered tricycle as a practical solution for short-distance transportation in urban areas. The tri-cycle integrates solar photovoltaic (PV) panels on its roof to harness clean and renewable energy from the sun, providing a continuous power source for propulsion. The research focuses on the technical aspects of the tricycle's construction, including the selection and integration of high-efficiency PV panels, the design of an efficient power management system, and the implementation of a lightweight yet durable frame structure. Additionally, the paper discusses the performance evaluation of the solar-powered tricycle, including energy efficiency, speed, and overall reliability. The results demonstrate that the solar-powered tricycle is capable of achieving sustainable mobility, with substantial reductions in carbon emissions and operational costs compared to traditional fossil fuel-powered vehicles. Furthermore, the study explores the potential socio-economic and environmental impacts of widespread adoption of solar-powered tricycles in urban transportation systems. The findings highlight the viability of solar-powered tricycles as a promising alternative for short-distance commuting, providing insights into the future of sustainable transportation.

Keywords: Solar-powered tri-cycle, sustainable transportation, renewable energy, solar panels, electric motor.

I. Background of the Study

Electric vehicles, as highlighted by Beedu (2015), utilize electric motors instead of internal combustion engines to generate motive force, operating solely on electric power. Solar-powered vehicles (SPVs), on the other hand, employ photovoltaic (PV) cells to convert sunlight into electricity, as noted by Ravikumar et al. (2013). The electricity generated by PV cells is either directed to an electric motor for propulsion or stored in a specialized battery. Notably, PV cells exclusively generate electricity in the presence of sunlight, necessitating stored electricity for solar-powered cars during periods of low solar exposure. Over the years, considerable efforts from inventors, government bodies, and industries have contributed to the development of solar-powered cars, boats, bicycles, and even airplanes (Gupta et al., 2010). In contrast to expensive car or motorcycle options, individuals have shown a preference for tricycles as their chosen means of transportation. Various types of tricycles, including pedal tricycles, motorized tricycles, and electric tricycles, are available. However, these tricycle options possess certain limitations. To address these

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weaknesses, this project aims to develop an enhanced tricycle design. Given Nigeria's location within the tropics, specifically in the Capricorn area, this project focuses on harnessing the underutilized solar energy in Enugu, Nigeria, to create a solar-powered hand tricycle primarily intended for the mobility of disabled individuals.

The primary objective of this project is to facilitate easy transportation and mobility for individuals with physical disabilities. The mobility challenges faced by the physically disabled population are well-documented in society. Currently, physically disabled individuals rely on assistive devices such as crutches, artificial limbs, manual wheelchairs, or three-wheelers for their daily movements. However, these wheelchairs or three-wheelers often have crude and inefficient designs, rendering them unsuitable for outdoor use or navigating common terrains in the country. In certain rural communities and other areas, hand-powered tricycles are being utilized to provide mobility for disabled persons. In this project, we have undertaken the design and manufacturing of a system that converts the hand-powered tricycle into a solar-operated electric motor-powered version (Ravikumar et al., 2012). The tricycle will be self-operated and independent, harnessing unlimited solar energy from the sun. The proposed solar-powered three-wheeler features a lightweight and moderately-sized structure. Cost efficiency is achieved through the utilization of locally available resources such as pipes for chassis/body, wheels, bearings, etc. Additionally, the required components like batteries, motors, and solar panels are readily accessible in the market. These attributes collectively make the solar three-wheeler an affordable and environmentally-friendly transport solution for the daily needs of disabled individuals.

II. Overview of the Study

Since the advent of the industrial revolution, the rate of energy consumption has risen drastically due to the combined impact of individual energy usage and population growth. To address this challenge, the mass production of photovoltaic (PV) cells that convert solar energy into stable electrical energy can offer a solution. Photovoltaic cells harness the sun's energy to generate electrical power (Fiyanshu et al., 2016). Utilizing this technology enables the operation of solar vehicles, alleviating pressure on the energy sector and promoting environmental sustainability. Although solar-powered vehicles are not yet widespread, the integration of renewable energy sources, particularly solar photovoltaic power, plays a crucial role in reducing CO₂ emissions and creating a pollution-free environment, as exemplified in the case of the tricycle discussed here (Sakar et al., 2016).

The fundamental working principle of a solar-assisted tricycle lies in utilizing an electric motor powered by solar energy to provide motion, thereby eliminating environmental pollution associated with internal combustion engines. In solar-powered vehicles (SPVs), the electric motor is directly powered by the electricity generated from sunlight by photovoltaic (PV) cells. When sunlight is available, PV cells produce electricity, which powers the electric motor for propulsion. In the absence of sunlight, energy is drawn from the vehicle's batteries. Tricycles come in different types, including paddle tricycles, motorized tricycles, and electric tricycles. Paddle tricycles require significant physical effort to pedal, leading to user fatigue. This becomes particularly challenging for students who find it difficult to concentrate on their studies after exerting themselves by pedaling a paddle tricycle.

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Next, the motorized tricycle operates on fuel, which is expensive and has a detrimental impact on the environment by contributing to global warming. In contrast, the electric tricycle relies on a battery system powered by solar energy (Ravikumar et al., 2016). In terms of promoting a healthy city environment, the electric tricycle proves to be the superior choice among the three types of tricycles. It emits fewer pollutants, allowing city dwellers to commute without perspiring excessively while providing an eco-friendly alternative to traditional cars. Table 1 below presents a compilation of solar-powered vehicles constructed in different regions worldwide, highlighting their construction costs, years of development, locations, and features. Additionally, a hybrid solar vehicle prototype has been developed for conducting various experimental activities (Mahadi et al., 2017). Furthermore, a discussion is conducted to compare the environmental impacts of solar power-assisted vehicles with conventional internal combustion engines. The primary objective of this tricycle design is to enhance efficiency and reduce costs to make it accessible to all individuals. The alarming increase in CO₂ emissions from 12 billion metric tons in 1965 to 32 billion metric tons in 2010 AD (Devaneyan, 2016) demonstrates the urgent need to address global warming. By using solar-powered tricycles, we can contribute to reducing environmental pollution and combating climate change.

i. The electric tri-cycle

The Electric Tricycle design is based on adapting existing hand-powered tricycles with minimal modifications (Hofman et al., 2007). It incorporates an electric motor, a drive system, motor and steering controls, and a power supply. The availability of electricity in Nigeria and the presence of a solar array at the Handicap Center make solar energy an ideal source for battery recharging. The drive system was the first aspect addressed, focusing on transmitting power from the electric motor to the rear wheel. A simple mechanical joystick was chosen to control motor speed and braking, ensuring ease of use for individuals with limited dexterity. The hand-power system was replaced with a steering system that disables hand-power capability. The motor is powered by a battery pack. All components (motor, transmission, controls, batteries) are designed to be easily installed on existing hand-powered tricycles, and the conversion process is reversible, allowing for flexibility and adaptability.

A photovoltaic module, commonly known as a solar panel, consists of interconnected photovoltaic cells that generate electricity from solar energy. These panels are used as components in larger photovoltaic systems to provide power for various commercial and residential applications (Mohan, 2009). The main challenge associated with solar power, as well as wind power, has been its efficiency. The Earth receives an abundant amount of solar radiation, which is more than sufficient to meet the energy demands of our species. Similarly, wind energy is estimated to be four times greater than what our species currently consumes each year. Solar power is particularly remarkable, as the sun provides more energy to the planet in a single day than we use in an entire year. Therefore, the availability of sun and wind has never been the issue; they are readily accessible sources of energy.

Figure 1: skeletal model of the existing system

ii. *Advantages & Disadvantages of Solar Energy System*

a) Advantages:

1. Solar energy is environmentally friendly as it does not produce any pollution or harmful gases, unlike burning oil or fossil fuels.
2. Solar energy is a renewable resource, ensuring a constant and consistent power source even during cloudy or stormy days.
3. Despite the initial cost of solar panels and lighting, they lead to significant long-term savings as harnessing the power of the sun is free, unlike paying for expensive oil.
4. Solar panels and products are easy to install, eliminating the need for complex wiring or power sources.
5. Solar power technology continues to improve, offering numerous benefits as people recognize the advantages of this sustainable energy source.
6. Solar cells require minimal maintenance and have a long lifespan, with only annual cleaning needed.
7. Solar cells operate silently, in contrast to noisy machinery used in oil extraction.
8. Solar-powered vehicles have fewer moving parts, resulting in reduced service requirements compared to conventional cars.
9. Solar-powered vehicles produce no emissions since there is no internal combustion engine or combustion taking place.
10. Electric vehicles, powered by solar energy, are exceptionally quiet due to the absence of noisy engines.

11. Solar-powered vehicles do not require refueling in the traditional sense, relying solely on sunlight for operation.
12. Solar-powered vehicles do not contribute to additional emissions from power plants since they don't rely on utility-generated electricity.
13. Solar-powered vehicles demonstrate exceptional energy efficiency, achieving greater mileage per unit of energy compared to traditional gasoline-powered cars.

b) Disadvantages:

1. Solar energy generation is dependent on sunlight availability, which can be limited during nighttime or in areas with frequent cloud cover.
2. The initial installation cost of solar panels and equipment can be relatively high, although the long-term savings offset this expense.
3. Energy storage is necessary for sustained power supply during periods of low sunlight, adding to the overall system cost.
4. Solar energy systems require a significant amount of space for the installation of solar panels to generate sufficient power.

III. Design Methodology

i. Working Principle of the System

The system operates based on the following principle: The solar panels capture solar energy from the sun and convert it into direct current (DC) using a voltage converter. This DC energy is then stored in 5-volt deep cell batteries located on the motor frame. A microcontroller, acting as a digital computer, controls the logic and arithmetic operations of the system. It also regulates the radio frequency unit to activate the DC motor simultaneously. The operation of the solar-powered tricycle system, as illustrated in Figure 2, can be wirelessly controlled using a radio frequency protocol. The system includes a control pad that indicates the motor's direction. Additionally, the solar panel serves the purpose of battery charging to ensure continuous operation of the system.

Figure 2: System block diagram

ii. Construction

The construction of the system is based on the mathematical model described in chapter three of this work, and it is implemented using the components selected as discussed in the same chapter. To enhance acceleration and maximum speed, the chassis is designed to be lightweight. The choice of materials for the chassis is crucial, as they need to possess sufficient strength to withstand the vehicle's load and the weight of the driver. Mild Steel Pipe is a suitable material due to its comparatively low weight and high strength, making it capable of supporting the driver, vehicle, and light loads. The power transmission from the battery to the wheel is achieved through a chain drive, which is clearly illustrated in figure 3.

Figure 3: power transmission from motor to wheel

Figure 4 and Figure 5 represent the Conceptual view and Experimental view of the tri-cycle showing all the main parts and required dimensions.

Figure 4: conceptual view of the system

Here, d = tricycle wheel rim diameter in the meter, r = tricycle wheel rim radius in meter, ω = Angular velocity of the tricycle in rad/s., N = Speed of tricycle wheel in RPM, v = Speed of tricycle in km/h, the N_1 = Normal reaction of the road on each tire of the tricycle in Newton. , μ = Coefficient of friction = 0.3, F = Frictional force between tire and

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road in Newton, T =Torque developed on the shaft due to frictional force in N-m, P = Power required riding the tricycle in Watt, I =Moment of inertia in m^4 .

Figure 5: experimental view of the system

The testing of the features of the tri-cycle was carried out in stages. Each module was test after and during construction using multi-meter as the only test instrument. All modules were tested component by component. Each component tested yielded approximately the expected result. A few components however failed and were replaced in the process of testing.

IV. Performance Evaluation and Results

The system's performance closely matched the expected outcome, achieving approximately 95% of the expected result. The software successfully detected a faulty IC, ensuring reliable operation. The battery was connected to the motor, powering the solar tricycle during its operation. As the tricycle ran, the battery gradually discharged, following a linear pattern. Figure 4.4 illustrates the relationship between the charge levels (%) and the tricycle's running time, clearly demonstrating the decrease in stored energy over time due to consumption. The discharge profile of the battery, combined with the solar panel, is also depicted in Figure 4.4. In this figure, the charge level decreases from 100% to 15%. Although the discharge curve should theoretically be linear, a slight deviation from linearity is observed in Figure 6. It took approximately 3 hours for the battery to discharge fully. Analyzing the discharge curve, it was

observed that the battery lost 8% of its stored energy in the first half hour. Subsequently, the discharge percentages for each subsequent half hour were 17%, 15%, 11%, 14%, and 20%, respectively.

Figure 6: analysis of battery charging rate per day

Figure 7 shows the two curves of discharging the battery. The green line on the curve indicates discharging the battery without solar panel and the red line indicates discharging the battery when the solar is acting. Red line curve passed over the green line curve because some charge was accumulated in the battery during discharging. As a result, the red line ends at 31 km which is 6 km far from the green line end point. It shows the performance of solar assisted tricycle. So by activating the solar panel during discharge of the battery, solar tricycle runs more 24% than the running without the solar panel.

Figure 7: charger with and without solar energy

V. Conclusion

This work has developed a tri-cycle mobility machine to help in the locomotion of the disabled. It has been a challenge to provide a low economic and fuel-less means for movement and transportation for the handicapped. This work

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presented a solar powered motor cycle using the natural heat energy generated from the sun to power a d.c motor. The goal of the solar operated Tricycle is to bring increased mobility to disable persons. This three-wheeler is operated by solar power and suitable for outdoor use. Solar power option enables the disabled people to use it at any place, even in remote areas where there is no electricity. The renewable energy is vital for today's world as in near future the non renewable sources that we are using are going to get exhausted. The solar vehicle is a step in saving these non renewable sources of energy. The main content of the solar tricycle is solar PV panel, brushless DC motor and battery. This idea, in future, may help to protect our fuels from getting extinguished.

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